

Dear artist,

We kindly invite you to participate in our **research project** “SpART: Spotlight on Artists in Recommenders Systems”, which is a collaboration between the Music Technology Group at the **University of Pompeu Fabra** (Barcelona) and the Institute of Computational Perception at the **Johannes Kepler University Linz**. The purpose of this project is to understand how current systems used to recommend music affect artists and to propose alternative solutions that could benefit the artists.

Music recommender systems are used in streaming services (e.g., Spotify, YouTube), they provide recommended music to users based on their musical taste, listening activity, or mood. Some examples of recommender systems are automatic playlist generation (e.g., Spotify’s personalized ‘discover weekly’ or unpersonalized ‘popular music from the 90s’), suggestions to add tracks to an existing playlist, or artists suggested based on your previous listening behavior.

For this, **we invite you to participate in an interview of 60 minutes**. In this interview, we will first explain in non-technical terms how current music recommender systems work (10 minutes), and proceed with interview questions (max 50 minutes) regarding your experience with recommender systems from your perspective as an artist. The goal is to identify potential problems that affect artists, and to draw on your ideas about how you would like future recommender systems to work.

With your participation you will give voice to the artists’ perspective, which is very important to allow for building recommender systems that consider the artists’ needs.

We assure that all information from the interviews will be held strictly confidential. Only anonymized data will be reported in possible scientific publications; this means that your identity as a participant will remain confidential at all times. SpART is a fundamental research project without any commercial purpose, goal, or beneficiary involved.

Please contact us with date suggestions for the interview. We are happy to meet at a place in Vienna/Linz/Barcelona. Of course, you are heartily welcome at our institute in Linz/Barcelona. If you prefer an interview via Video Skype or a similar communication tool, we could also arrange for that.

We thank you for your participation and look forward to talking to you and building a basis for better music recommender systems that benefit artists.

Best regards,
Andrés Ferraro
Dr. Christine Bauer